

ONLINE FURNITURE SHOP

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Abstract. The Online Furniture Shop project is a platform designed to make buying and managing furniture online easy and efficient. It uses modern web technologies to provide a complete and smooth shopping experience for customers while simplifying tasks for administrators. Key features include a detailed product catalog, advanced filtering options, customer reviews, and a secure checkout process. The project uses PHP, JavaScript, Bootstrap, HTML, CSS, jQuery, and MySQL to improve both customer satisfaction and store management.

Keywords: online furniture shop, e-commerce, product management, customer experience

INTRODUCTION

In today's digital world, an effective online furniture shop system is important for providing a smooth shopping experience and easy management. This project aims to create a reliable platform that supports various tasks like product management, customer interactions, and order processing. The motivation behind this project is to make shopping convenient for customers and managing the store simple for administrators. By using modern design principles and technology, the Online Furniture Shop aims to enhance efficiency, increase customer satisfaction, and support business growth.

PROBLEM

Traditional furniture stores present several challenges, including limited operating hours, geographical constraints, and a lack of variety in product offerings. Customers often struggle with the inconvenience of physically visiting stores and limited stock availability. Additionally, managing orders, stock levels, and customer inquiries is labor-intensive for business owners, reducing efficiency. There was a need for a streamlined solution that provides easier access for customers and effective management tools for admins.

APPROACH

The project adopts a web-based solution to address these problems by allowing customers to browse and purchase furniture online at their convenience. Key features such as product searches, real-time stock updates, and notifications when stock is low enhance the

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customer experience. Admins are provided with an intuitive panel to manage orders, products, and deliveries efficiently. Technologies like Bootstrap, jQuery, and a PHP/MySQL backend were used to ensure responsiveness, dynamic functionality, and secure data handling. The system also supports secure payment methods like Kpay, WavePay, and cash on delivery.

Customers can access the platform to either register or log in, after which they can browse product categories, view item details, add items to their wishlist or cart, and adjust quantities. Admins log in to the dashboard, where they can manage key aspects of the platform, including product management (adding, updating, deleting products), organizing categories, and handling customer orders and messages. They also manage customer accounts, updating or adding customers and setting permissions.

Figure 1: System Flow Diagram

Figure 2: Database Design

An Entity Relationship Diagram uses data modeling techniques that can help define business processes and serve as the foundation for a relational database. An ERD attribute can be denoted as a primary key, which identifies a unique attribute, or a foreign key, which can be assigned to multiple attributes. A cardinality notation can then define the attributes of the relationship between the entities. The ER (Entity-Relationship) diagram for the user side of the Online Furniture Shop system represents the various entities involved and their relationships. Key entities include customers, Products, Categories, Orders, Reviews, and Messages.

RESULTS

The implemented system successfully created an efficient platform for both users and administrators. Customers can now enjoy an intuitive shopping experience, while admins can effectively manage products, orders, and stock levels. The system's multilingual support broadens its accessibility, and future enhancements, such as advanced filtering and expanded product offerings, promise to further improve the user experience. The platform has achieved its goal of simplifying the furniture purchasing process while providing essential features for future.

Figure 3: Implementation of this system

CONCLUSION

The online furniture shop project has effectively delivered a user-friendly platform that simplifies the process of finding and purchasing furniture. Key features, including detailed product views, an intuitive checkout process, and efficient order management, enhance the overall shopping experience. By using modern design and technology, the platform has improved accessibility and convenience for customers. Looking ahead, there are opportunities to further enhance the shop by incorporating personalized recommendations, expanding mobile functionality, and integrating additional features to better meet customer needs and stay competitive in the market.

REFERENCES

- [1] Chen, H.Freth “ The Role of Real-Time Data in E-Commerce Systems”, Journal of Information Technology Management, 25(1), 60-75, 2019
- [2] Thompson “Responsive Web Design for Online Shopping Platforms, Web and Mobile Interface Design Review” 19(2), 52-67, 2014.
- [3] Patel, D.Mord “Scalability Challenges in E-Commerce Systems”, Journal of Software Engineering Practices 13(3), 88-103, 2011.
- [4] Roberts, “Comparative Analysis of Online vs Offline Shopping Management Systems” , 11(4), 30-44, 2016.